

SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONTENT OF IMPROVING EFFICIENCY MANAGEMENT IN SERVICE ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. This article discusses increasing the efficiency of service enterprises, properly organizing management activities, innovative management of service networks, increasing the potential of personnel, improving mechanisms for the use of economic resources, increasing labor productivity, improving the quality of services, meeting the needs of consumers to the maximum issues such as meeting the level.

Keywords: Efficiency, labor productivity, service economy, management.

Introduction. The development of service networks and the increase of efficiency indicators in them is determined by the proper organization of social and economic management. In today's economic reforms, economical use of economic resources is the demand of the time. This is a never-ending problem, and the lack of economic resources is a pressing issue facing every country. That is why scientists and specialists are still thinking about this issue. In our opinion, economic efficiency has clear indicators, and its proper management is evident to a certain extent. Identifying factors affecting economic efficiency and eliminating them are the main tasks of economic enterprises. Ensuring social efficiency is considered to be a change in people's lifestyle for the better, and serves as the main criterion for increasing economic efficiency.

Analysis of literature on the topic. In order to develop the economy of the service sector, several scientists are conducting scientific research. A number of scientists such as M.Q.Pardayev, A.Abdullayev, E.S.Fayziyev, R.M.Gaibullayev, Sh.Rozinazarov, I.S.Ochilov can be included among these.

Analysis and results

Today, the rational use of labor resources in service enterprises depends on the competitiveness of personnel working in this sector. For this reason, increasing the knowledge potential of workers in the field is a matter of particular importance. The competitiveness of service personnel is determined on the basis of many factors. We can include physiological, professional skills, self-expression, social-psychological, ideological, spiritual growth.

The experience of foreign countries with developed economies shows that the application of the achievements of scientific and technical development (STD) in all types of services to the labor process is not uniformly accepted, which, in turn, has a sufficient impact on performance indicators. For example, services with a subjective nature related to catering may not be very suitable for standardization and technicalization. These types of services, even if they rapidly adopt the achievements of STD, they cannot quickly achieve high results and efficiency, because in such activities, it depends on the desire, demand, need and level of service of the consumer. If they are at a low level, this process will have a negative impact on

the growth rate of service efficiency. It should be said that information technology does not have a very positive effect on increasing productivity in these types of services.

Table 1.

It is appropriate to pay special attention to social criteria in the development of the service industry. Continuous and high-quality performance of any process depends on the skills and knowledge of the employees working there. Improving the quality of service, meeting customer demand, and being able to correctly use management functions to achieve quality efficiency is the main focus of management.

Service activity is a complex and multifaceted process. This process is ensured by good management of the company's employees and resources, compliance with the standards of service provision, and satisfaction of the needs of the provided services in accordance with the requirements of consumers.

Table 2.

At the same time, agreeing with the opinion of N.G.Fedko, the following features can be distinguished in the process of effective economic activity that occurs with the development of service activities.

1. Business entities in the service economy pay attention to increasing social and economic efficiency, that is, to more fully satisfy the private requirements of each consumer. In the industrial economy, the main attention is directed to the maximum production of goods.
2. The concept of efficiency in the field of services is the same as the description of the use of goods, and it determines the extent to which the system of material goods and services is modernized. In the industrial economy, only the material side of the product is taken into account.
3. In service industries, the ability to constantly control and determine the demand of the producer to meet the full needs of the consumer is assumed based on the quality criterion. In the field of production, based on the quality criterion, only the qualitative performance of the operator is taken into account.
4. The management system in the service sector is also changing. Its main characteristics are flexibility, speed of decision-making, organizational aspect, free activity, self-expression and transparency, while in industrial economy, management is determined by the composition, hierarchical appearance and regulation of organizational structures.
5. In the service sector, the main attention is focused on the formation of service quality and its effectiveness, while in the industrial economy, efforts are made to turn raw materials into finished products.

If we conclude from the given opinions and considerations, increasing the efficiency of economic activity in the service sector differs sharply from the effective activity in the industrial economy and, as we can see, it is distinguished by the unique feature of the social orientation of the labor process.

Increasing the efficiency of service provision, rapid development of this sector is one of the important requirements of today's period of economic reforms. Efficiency is an indicator that reflects the economic stability and ability to operate any enterprise.

Science and technology development has been an important factor in increasing the efficiency of service activities of enterprises and has not lost its importance even now. This factor can be used in the following ways:

- Automation and comprehensive mechanization of work in service provision;
- Robotization of the main technological processes, use of digital technologies;
- Implementation of progressive technological processes aimed at saving labor and resources and their wide use;
- Use of modern information technologies and computing equipment in the processes of organization, planning and management of service provision;
- Scientific organization of work in service provision.

In practice, it is almost impossible to find an enterprise that denies or does not understand the importance and role of scientific and technical progress, including its components. However, only desires and wishes are not enough to implement this factor. For this, firstly, to search for and identify currently necessary directions of science and technology development, secondly, to find funds and other necessary resources, and thirdly, design, technological and other scientific institutions specializing in modern scientific and technical developments. It is required to "connect" the necessary connections with, fourthly, to calculate the efficiency of one's scientific and technical goals.

Until recently, the development of science and technology was developing in an evolutionary way. The main focus was on the improvement of existing technologies, partial modernization of machines and equipment. Such measures brought certain limited results.

Interest in the development and implementation of new techniques was not at the level of demand. Foreign progressive technologies of service provision and labor organization were perceived as "a sign of exploitation", and automation and mechanization of service provision were perceived as the basis of unemployment. Foreign experiments were regarded as capitalist experiments, and the wide spread of these experiments was not allowed.

In the current conditions, where economic reforms are flourishing, it is necessary to make deep quality changes, transition to the principles of new technologies and the latest generation equipment, and to rearm all sectors of the economy based on the latest achievements of science and technology. At the same time, it is important to create economic and social interests for scientists, designers, engineers and workers to work in a creative spirit. For example, creative groups and quality groups are organized in Japanese enterprises and firms. These are being developed in connection with universities, scientific centers and laboratories, which are inextricably linked with the development of technology. It is no coincidence that today Japan ranks first in the creation of robots and other types of modern techniques and technologies.

Organizational and economic factors, including management, play an important role in improving the efficiency of service activities of enterprises. Their importance increases with the growth of the scale of service provision and the complexity of economic relations. Among these factors, in the first place, it is possible to include the creation of reasonable forms of service provision and the improvement of existing ones - service cooperation cluster.

And in management, it is expressed in the improvement of the methods and forms of management, planning, economic stimulation, that is, the entire economic mechanism of enterprise activity. The work style and methods of the head of the enterprise must be compatible with the technological development and the market economy. For example, the director of the enterprise should be higher than ordinary employees and heads of department services according to his knowledge, experience and professional qualifications. Otherwise, it

is difficult for him to be able to manage the team in the right way and to achieve success, as well as increase the efficiency of management.

Conclusion. To sum up, the service sector is a process with an important indicator in the development of the country's economy. Factors such as improving the display structure also play an important role. This is achieved through the use of modern machines and equipment, modern production technologies and advanced methods of labor organization. Of course, the implementation of the above-mentioned factors requires the use of certain resources and time. However, this does not change the essence and importance of mammos. Practice shows that an enterprise that keeps pace with the times, observes savings in all types of activities, uses its potential more efficiently, relies on modern science and technology achievements, ensures that it will achieve success in the future in addition to its current success.

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